

deepnic.cyens.org.cy

DEEP NIC

Mapping Nicosia's
urban centre
1960-2020

Monument Building
in the urban centre of Nicosia,
1960-2020: An overview.

August 2023

Monument Building in the urban centre of Nicosia, 1960-2020: An overview.

Antigone Heraclidou

CYENS Centre of Excellence/ Cyprus University of Technology and

Esra Plümer Bardak

Association for Historical Dialogue and Research

INTRODUCTION

As it has been shown in several documentations and studies, monuments, statues, or memorials, are among the most visible expressions of collective identity and by their physicality, they necessarily represent a selective interpretation of the past that is given permanent and, seemingly, immutable expression in stone or metal.¹ Monuments, statues, memorial sites and even street names, may incite, as the novelist Pamuk said when referring to monuments in Istanbul, painful emotions over everything that has been lost.² Conversely, they could incite feelings of pride, honour, or justice. Furthermore, in many countries monuments or memorials are testimonials of parallel and conflicting historical narratives. Challenging these narratives, as experienced recently in several countries with colonial or slavery connections, has also become evident in the perception of and stance against monuments leading to cases where monuments were abruptly brought down, damaged, relocated or faced with a counter monument.

Historical narrative, memory, and identity formation are strongly linked to the decisions taken behind the erection of a monument in a public space. This is especially true in places with a difficult past. Cyprus makes an interesting and, to some extent, unique case of a place which, despite its small size, has experienced for decades monument building serving two parallel historical narratives, and two distinct national orientations.

Following up on previous works related to monument building in Cyprus, this project comes to document monuments, museums,

NOTES

- 1 Timothy W Ryback, Dr Mark S Ellis and Benjamin Glahn, eds. *International Bar Association Task Force Report: Contested Histories in Public Spaces: Principles, Processes, Best Practices*, (London: International Bar Association, 2021), 14.
- 2 Anita Bakshi, "A shell of memory: The Cyprus conflict and Nicosia's walled city," *Memory Studies* 5, no.4 (October: 2012): 485

and cultural centres erected or operated across the divide between 1960 and 2020 and to what extent their emergence is related to or affected by certain key events i.e. the establishment of the Republic of Cyprus in 1960; the intercommunal strife in 1963-1964; the 1974 war; the introduction of the Nicosia Master Plan in 1979; the unilateral proclamation of a new regime in the Turkish Cypriot community in 1983; the introduction of a new law that allowed the employment of third country workers in Cyprus in 1991; the opening of the crossings in 2003; the entry of the Republic of Cyprus into the European Union; the economic crisis of 2013 and the outbreak of the pandemic in 2020. These are significant political and socio-economic events that have marked the recent history of Cyprus and affected the course of the island across the divide, although not equally for the two communities. Our aim was to examine whether the type and intensity of monument and museum building can be related to these events and whether these events are reflected in these monuments.

For the purposes of this study we included in the broad category of monuments any sculptures erected or museums established during this period. Busts or statues usually portray personalities or groups of people who have played a role in events considered significant by their (respective) communities or contributed to their community's economic, social, cultural development or well-being. It was therefore essential that in a study related to the turbulent history of the island, busts and statues are included. Equally, museums in Nicosia cannot be overlooked by this project, since the political events that occurred after 1960 are inevitably reflected in the island's museums.³ In their book, Stylianos-Lambert and Bounia discuss the history of theory creation, the use of objects, their depiction of the "Other" and the commemorative styles and prove the point that museums can be influential in periods of conflict and help construct collective memories and ethno-national identities.⁴

Cultural activity is surely not limited to monument building or museums as it includes different forms of art as well. Indeed, art practices and cultural activity have multiplied over the years and a correlation between artistic and cultural activity in Nicosia and political developments can definitely be drawn. For example, Evi Tselika's report on *Conflict Transformation Art*, considers how art practices in Cyprus have been used in the context of conflict transformation and investigates the role arts can play to help people from both communities' experience coexistence in their daily lives.⁵ However, these deserve a study of their own and for practical reasons this overview could not offer a comprehensive analysis of such practices.

NOTES

- 3 Theopisti Stylianos-Lambert and Alexandra Bounia, *The Political Museum: Power, Conflict, and Identity in Cyprus* (London and New York: Routledge, 2016), 16. The book's main argument is that politics directly influences identity, and it reveals how policies are interwoven in all facets of museums.
- 4 Stylianos Lambert and Bounia, *The Political Museum*, 17&119.
- 5 Evanthia Tselika, *Conflict Transformation Art: Cultivating coexistence through the use of socially engaged artistic practices*, (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, Report: 4, 2019).

The historical context

Cyprus has been under successive empires for centuries before becoming an independent country. As part of the Ottoman Empire for more than 300 years, from 1571 until 1878, a significant Muslim community that enjoyed a privileged treatment, compared to non-muslim populations, was living on the island. This disproportionate balance of power, rights and privileges existed between the two communities, during this time, changed with the introduction of British rule in 1878 with the reorganisation of the justice system. However, the existence of two separate communities, each with a distinct ethnic identity, religion, language and national orientation, in what was supposed to be a British Colony, continued, and grew stronger during the British colonial rule, to an extent that on the one hand impeded the development of a common Cypriot identity, and to another it could not be sidelined with the establishment of one independent Republic for all the communities. The end to British rule came after an armed revolt carried out by EOKA⁶ during which intercommunal rivalry culminated with each community becoming more clinched on their national goals, i.e. *enosis* (union with Greece) for Greek Cypriots and *taksim* (division of the island into two parts) for Turkish Cypriots. This is not the time or the space to discuss the origins or the development of these national aspirations, but their inculcation within Cypriot society was so strong that it persisted even after the end of the British rule. In fact, as Joseph argues, the removal of the Colonial Administration left the way open for the two motherlands to develop close relations with the newborn state and seek promotion of their national goals on the island.⁷ The establishment of the new Republic in 1960 was accompanied with a Treaty of Guarantee, signed between the Republic of Cyprus, Greece, Turkey, and the United Kingdom. According to this Treaty, the guarantor powers pledged to recognize and guarantee the independence, territorial integrity and security of the Republic and they undertook to prohibit any activity promoting, directly or indirectly, either union of Cyprus with any other state or partition of the island.⁸ This aimed at preventing the repetition of actions aiming at *enosis* or *taksim*, but at the same time, three other countries were given a role and a say over an independent and sovereign state, something that is partly reflected on the continuing attachment of the two communities to their national centres.

In fact, the 1960 Constitution itself formally segregated the two communities in many vital areas, such as education. This provides an explanation as to why monument building observed after the establishment of the island's independence resonates with each community's national aspirations that pre-existed the new Republic, instead of focusing on events or personalities that have or might bring the two closer to each other or built on, as Pollis wrote, their shared historical legacy and culture that differentiated them from the Greeks of Greece and the Turks of Turkey.⁹

A prominent role in Nicosia's built heritage is held by the

NOTES

- 6 EOKA stands for National Organisation of Cypriot fighters (Ethniki Organosi Kypriwn Agwnistwn) which was a guerilla organization that fought towards overthrowing the colonial rule in Cyprus during 1955-1959 and uniting the island with Greece
- 7 Joseph S. Joseph, *Cyprus: Ethnic Conflict and International Politics* (London: MacmillanPress, 1997), 39–40.
- 8 United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Island, Greece and Turkey and Cyprus, No.5475. *Treaty of Guarantee*, 16 August 1960, United Nations -Treaty Series, p.2 ;<https://peacemaker.un.org/cyprus-greece-turkey-guarantee60#:~:text=This%20treaty%20is%20part%20of,or%20partition%20of%20the%20Island>. Accessed 10.07.2023
- 9 Adamantis Pollis, "The social construction of ethnicity and nationalism: The case of Cyprus", *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics* 2, no. 1 (1996): 69

Venetian walls which Bakshi in her *Topographies of Memory* has described as a “shell of memory”, or as “a screen onto which certain national, historical constructs can be projected”.¹⁰ While *Topographies of Memory* focuses on the relationship between current memory discourses and urban design and planning purposes, this project explores the construction of memory through monumental building. The space within the Venetian walls, the walled city across the divide, holds a prominent place in this analysis as it can become the object for comparison between the present and the past, for the past is seen and remembered differently by the two communities. This is, in fact, reflected in the monuments erected in the post-1960 period.

The monument building that took place in the centre of Nicosia after 1960 makes an interesting case. Nicosia is the capital of Cyprus, and therefore the place where most political events were felt more intensely. In 1956, the city centre was divided by a barbed wire separating the Turkish from the Greek sector, a measure against inter-communal conflict. This line was cemented in 1964 following the intercommunal violence that erupted in December 1963, and became known as the Green Line, patrolled by a United Nations force. Since 1964 then, Nicosia has been divided into two ‘sides’, one to the north, and the other to the south of the Green Line, each of them evolving differently. The 1974 war concluded the division of the two communities and the city itself, a situation that remains in force until today. The Republic of Cyprus, established in 1960, has control over more than half of the island, south of the Green Line, while north of the Green Line, a Turkish Cypriot administration is in power. The Turkish Cypriot regime is not recognized internationally except by Turkey which apart from the military presence it maintains on the island since 1974, it supports the regime financially. Since 1974, there have been many attempts by the two sides to negotiate a solution to what has been termed ‘The Cyprus Problem’, with the involvement of the international community, but none of them succeeded although in certain cases like in 1978, 2004 and 2017, negotiations made such progress that reaching an agreement seemed possible.

The monuments or museums emerged on either side of the Green Line in Nicosia after 1960 commemorate different events and serve different narratives and aims, either as the community’s effort to “keep the collective trauma alive”¹¹, or as part of a physical manifestation of belonging to a community.¹² As a result, most monuments in the Greek Cypriot community commemorate the EOKA struggle and the 1974 war while in the Turkish Cypriot community, most monuments honour and commemorate the actions of the TMT¹³ or the leaders of the community. A prominent position in the monument building is held by historical figures, different for each community, i.e. Archbishop Makarios III (1913-1977) for Greek Cypriots; Former

NOTES

- 10 Anita Bakshi, *Topographies of Memories: A new Poetics of Commemoration* (Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017), 197
- 11 Karaïskou, Vicky. “Commemorative Sculpture and Ceremonial Behaviors in the Public Sphere: Cyprus as a Case Study.” *Sociology Study* 3, no. 12 (December 2013): 921. Another project on monuments in Cyprus is “Iconoclastic Controversies: A visual sociology of statues and commemoration sites in the southern regions of Cyprus”, by Nico Carpentier. <http://nicocarpentier.net/iconoclastic/> Accessed: 23 August 2023. The project was recently extended to the northern part of Cyprus and presented at an exhibition at the Home for Cooperation in April 2022, under the title *The Mirror of Conflict Iconoclastic Controversies 2*.
- 12 Andreas Papallas, “Nationalism, Cultural Identities and Urban Conflicts as Shaped within the Contested Space of Nicosia”, in *Identity, Belonging and Human Rights: A Multi-Disciplinary Perspective*, ed. Nasia Hadjigeorgiou (United Kingdom: Inter-Disciplinary Press, 2016), 48.
- 13 TMT stands for Turkish Resistance Organisation (Türk Mukavemet Teşkilatı), a paramilitary organization aiming to counter EOKA’s goal for union of Cyprus with Greece

Figure 1:
Zubeyde Ali Rıza (Atatürk's
mother) bust,
Image by Esra Plümer Bardak

President of Turkey Mustafa Kemal Atatürk (1881-1938) or Former Vice President of Cyprus Fazıl Küçük (1906-1984) for Turkish Cypriots, transforming public spaces into an extended cemetery, where the historical narration is built on the traces of sorrow, both individual and collective".¹⁴ Koiloran, on the other hand, who studied monument building in the northern part of the island, calls these monuments as "markers of history" that -especially those of Kemal Atatürk- "not only 'freeze' a remembrance to politicians and martyrs, but crystalize a patriarchal sense of 'national family'".¹⁵

In her research on and documentation of commemorative sculpture in Cyprus, Karaiskou shows that there are characteristic cases of memorials that "prove that commemoration in the Republic of Cyprus is inextricably linked to location which is either associated with an actual event of death or draws power from its relation to culturally symbolic institutional buildings, such as churches or schools".¹⁶ It is therefore not coincidental that several busts honouring EOKA fighters were erected in school yards or near the Parliament or in central avenues or in landmarks connected with major events, making therefore those monuments as "telling examples of the semantic power of location".¹⁷ Such examples are the busts of EOKA fighters Andreas Zakos (1931-1956) (outside the Pancyprian Gymnasium), Iacovos Patatsos (1934-1956) (outside Eleneion primary school) or of Markos Drakos (1932-1957) (very close to the Parliament). The same applies to monuments of the Turkish Cypriot community, such as the Monument of Martyrs (in front of the "legislative assembly") or the statue of Former Prime Minister of Turkey Mustafa Bülent Ecevit (in front of the Lycee that also carries his name). Location is important because it connects the monument with the space and this could be interpreted as a

NOTES

- ¹⁴ Vicky Karaiskou, "Commemorative Sculpture and Ceremonial Behaviors in the Public Sphere: Cyprus as a Case Study," *Sociology Study* 3, no. 12 (December 2013): 927
- ¹⁵ Moira Koiloran, "Nationalisms and Embodied Memory in Northern Cyprus, in *Cyprus and its people: nation, Identity, and Experience in Unimaginable Community*, ed. Vangelis Calotycho (Colorado: Westview Press, 1998, 1957-1999), 159-170, 162
- ¹⁶ Karaiskou, "Commemorative", 924. Vicky Karaiskou recorded all public art within the Republic of Cyprus. The results of the project are available through the project's website (<http://publicart.ouc.ac.cy/>) and the Open University of Cyprus official database, the "Kypseli" (Hive).
- ¹⁷ Karaiskou, "Commemorative", 926

reinforcement of the commemoration of an event or a reminder of what happened there in the past. Karaiskou's documentation of monuments is hitherto the most comprehensive available, while for the Turkish Cypriot community, a good source is the overview produced by Devrim Yücel Besim and Ayer Kaşif who examined fourteen selected monuments -some of these in the urban centre of Nicosia- all constructed between 1963 and 2012 and commemorate incidents that occurred between 1964-1974.¹⁸

Engagement with the public

In their overview, Besim and Kaşif observe that while the monuments memorialize important incidents and honour fallen soldiers or important personalities, they usually fail to relate to nearby environs or engage with the citizens, either due to their location and therefore lack of accessibility, or limited originality in their design, and thereby to assist with the sustainability of the city or transfer its memory to successive generations.¹⁹ Bülent Ecevit's statue, the *Martyrs' Monument* in Omorphita or the *Monument of Peace at Home Peace in the World* are merely some examples of monuments located in central avenues

Figure 2:

Markos Drakos statue.

Credits: Ioanna Christodoulou, 2023

NOTES

- ¹⁸ Devrim Yücel Besim and Ayer Kaşif, "An overview of Existing Monuments in Nicosia," *Journal of Cyprus Studies*, 19, no. 43, (Spring 2017): 67-81.
- ¹⁹ Besim and Kasif, "An overview of Existing Monuments", 68

Figure 3:

Bülent Ecevit statue,

Image by Esra Plümer Bardak

where traffic makes it difficult for the public to approach them on foot. The same applies to monuments of the Greek Cypriot community, such as the statue of Markos Drakos near Pafos Gate, or Kyriakos Matsis (1926-1958) statue near the Presidential Palace. Additionally, several statues remain unnoticed, either due to their location, i.e. overshadowed by tall buildings, such as the great benefactor Demosthenis Mitsis (1848-1923) (Arch. Makarios III Avenue) bust or the busts of the composer Marios Tokas (1954-2008) and the poet Kostas Montis (1914-2004) (Stasinou Avenue) or the lack of connection with its surroundings. For example, the imposing statue of the Greek poet Kostis Palamas (1859-1943), situated at the peripheral edge of the Nicosia Municipal Gardens or The Poet of Kostas Varotsos (1955-) -situated until recently in a municipal parking place- seemed irrelevant to their designated location and fail to grasp the attention of the public. Conversely, the lack of proportion of a statue makes it unmissable for the public. A classic case of a disproportionate statue is that of the ten-metre-high statue of Archbishop Makarios III, which locals called "Bic Mac". It was erected in the yard of the Archbishopric in 1987 and remained there for twenty-one years when his successor, Archbishop Chrysostomos I (1927-2007) decided to relocate the statue to the mountains, in Throni, where Makarios's tomb is located and replace it with a much smaller statue. People complained that the statue, which weighed eleven tones and was taller than two double-deckers, was out of proportion with its surroundings and the neo-classical character of the area.²⁰

NOTES

- ²⁰ Theodoulou, M. "Nicosia bids farewell to a towering figure", *The National News*, October 22, 2008, Accessed: 11.07. 2023 <https://www.thenationalnews.com/world/europe/nicosia-bids-farewell-to-a-towering-figure-1.561157>

Figure 4:

Photograph depicting the glass sculpture by Costas Varotsos, titled *The Poet*, in Nicosia, 1990 Photograph: Costakis Charalambous, To Mati 1216 © The Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia – Photographic Archive, Cyprus Donation: Costakis Charalambous

Figure 5:

Photograph depicting the statue of Archbishop Makarios III in the courtyard of the Archbishopric, Nicosia, 1990, To Mati 116 © The Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia – Photographic Archive, Cyprus

Absence of shared monuments

This project deals with a period of sixty years, during the largest part of which the island has been divided in two. While the period the Republic of Cyprus had control over the whole of the island lasted from 1960 until 1974 actual co-existence between the two communities in an independent state lasted only three years, from 1960-1963. During this period however, no shared monuments are documented, that speak of the shared history, cultural heritage, or coexistence of the two communities. Probably, the only monument devoted to the Greco-Turkish friendship and cooperation in Cyprus, is that of Derviş Ali Kavazoğlu (1924-1965) and Kostas Misioulis (1921-1965) - both members of left-wing political part AKEL and proponents of peace- in the village of Athienou, who were murdered in 1965 by the TMT. Conversely, monument building between 1960 and 1963 in Nicosia testifies to the distinct national aspirations of the two communities. Therefore, the majority of the monuments are of political nature, i.e. fallen fighters of EOKA or TMT, or political leaders. Even the seemingly less political statues such as the busts of Greek singer Sophia Vempe (1910-1978) or Greek intellectual Nicolaos Katalanos (1855-1933), as well as the statues of Greek poets Kostis Palamas and Dionysios Solomos (1798-1857), were erected as an expression of the close cultural relation between Greece and Cyprus. A brief background story behind each statue is offered in the table below (ANNEX I). On the same lines, in the northern part of the city, the Authors of the Avenue monument, or the statues of Kemal Tunç & Osman Balıkcıoğlu are expressions of the pride in Turkish identity and heritage. It might therefore be said that the reluctance shown by the population towards the establishment of the Republic in 1960, and the attachment of the communities to their respective national centres were reflected in the erection of monuments after 1960.

Figure 6:
 "Authors of the Avenue"
 Monument to William Shakespeare and Mehmet Akif Ersoy
 Image by Esra Plumer Bardak

Methodology, sources, and challenges

Hitherto, researchers have naturally given more emphasis to the great monuments erected during the Medieval and Ottoman periods. An impressive analysis and depiction of these was made through the *Exploring Nicosia's Monuments. Medieval & Ottoman Period* platform. It is a joint project of the Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia and the Cyprus Institute and the STARC team, which resulted in the creation of digital representations and visualisation applications related to the historic architectural heritage of Nicosia. This cooperation aimed to create novel digital material that would facilitate the study, promotion, exhibition, dissemination, and preservation of the city's historic building legacy. The platform includes fourteen medieval monuments, such as St. Sophia Cathedral, the Panagia Chrysaliniotissa church, Famagusta Gate, Kyrenia Gate, Pafos Gate, and others and twenty Ottoman monuments such as the Bayraktar mosque, the Büyük Han and others. Visitors had the opportunity to interact with virtual 3D models of the monuments and learn more about them by reading information and viewing related photographic material.

As to the more contemporary monuments, information is available to us thanks to the study of Vicky Karaiskou which recorded all public art in the southern part of Cyprus. The results of the project are available through the project's website (<http://publicart.ouc.ac.cy/>) and the Open University of Cyprus official database, the "Kypseli" (Hive) (<https://kypseli.ouc.ac.cy/handle/11128/403>)²¹. Karaiskou's work, which deals with commemorative sculpture and ceremonial behaviours in the public sphere using Cyprus as a case study, offers a detailed documentation of the monuments in the southern part of Nicosia. For the commemorative sculpture that was erected in the northern part of Nicosia, much information is provided through the study of Dervim Yücel Besim and Ayer Kaşif, titled "An Overview of Existing Monuments in Nicosia"²². These two studies have guided us through our research since they provided a very solid foundation to build on and fill in any gaps. We have consulted secondary sources, newspapers, or internet posts on social media groups that collect and share information on the history of Nicosia. However, not all the monuments were documented. Therefore, we had to do some on-the-field research around the walled town to locate any monuments that were not included in the available sources or any other printed or online repositories. This was also a good way to create a photographic archive of the monuments in their current situation which can become a useful tool both for this project, or any future projects on Nicosia, as well as for comparison purposes between the present, the past and the future.

One of the challenges we encountered during our research was the lack of information for all the monuments. Some of them,

NOTES

- 21** Karaiskou, "Commemorative", 920-932
Vicky Karaiskou recorded all public art within the Republic of Cyprus. The results of the project are available through the project's website (<http://publicart.ouc.ac.cy/>) and the Open University of Cyprus official database, the "Kypseli" (Hive) (<https://kypseli.ouc.ac.cy/handle/11128/403>).
- 22** Besim and Kasif, "An overview of Existing Monuments", 67-81

especially the smaller, more decorative sculptures, are rarely or not at all mentioned in the local press. Additionally, a few monuments were removed from their initial positions, or were left to the mercy of time and nature and were partly destroyed.

Results

The documentation of each monument searched to provide a comprehensive knowledge around it and therefore, this information had to be found:

- Location
- Creator of the monument
- Date of creation
- Date of placement
- Materiality
- Caption
- The background story

We managed to document eighty-three sculptures, monuments, and museums across the divide which are presented here in order of creation. For the purposes of this project, we limited our documentation to the urban centre of Nicosia, although there are several monuments that are worthy of documentation and analysis in the periphery of the city centre, such as the National Sovereignty Monument near Ayios Dometios crossing, or the Kyriacos Matsis statue outside the Presidential Palace. The last element which deals the history or any controversies around these monuments are not presented here but will be available either on the project's platform or other publications.

Figure 7:
Theatre statues (Kemal Tunç
& Osman Balikçioğlu),
Credits: Esra Plümer Bardak,
2023

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Nicolaos Katalanos bust

LOCATION

The bust used to be located in the old Eleftheria Square. Today, it is located in the "Anorthosis Football Club" Museum, in Larnaca.

CREATOR

Ioannis Notaras

DATE INAUGURATED

1960

Background Information

Nicolaos Katalanos (1855-1933) was a Greek intellectual, educationalist and journalist. He lived in Cyprus for a period of twenty years during which he significantly contributed to the development of the educational and intellectual activity on the island, and he became involved in the national movement for union with Greece. A committee of colleagues and students constructed a bust in his honor, which was initially placed in Eleftheria Square but was later removed during renovations and never re-installed. The bust was eventually placed in the Museum of the Anorthosis Football Club in Larnaca in 2023.

NAME

The National Struggle Museum

LOCATION

Archbishopric Square

DATE INAUGURATED

1961-1962

Background Information

The museum showcasing documents, photographs, personal belongings, and other memorabilia related to the EOKA struggle against British Rule is located in the square near the Archbishopric. It was founded after the end of the 1955-1959 EOKA revolt on the initiative of the Greek Communal Chamber and directed by the EOKA fighter Christodoulos Papachrysostomou. In 2001, new premises were designed and funded by the Holy Archbishopric of Cyprus and the Cyprus Ministry of Education and Culture.

NAME

Markos Drakos statue
on a column

LOCATION

Pafos Gate

CREATOR

Andreas Savvides

DATE INAUGURATED

1962

Background Information

Markos Drakos (1932-1957) was an EOKA fighter who died in 1957 at the age of 25 during a fight near the village of Evrychou. He led the team that attacked the Cyprus Broadcasting Station in Nicosia during the first EOKA attacks in April 1955. A statue was erected in his memory by the Confederation of Cypriot Workers (SEK) and Greek Cypriot donations, and it was inaugurated by President Archbishop Makarios III on October 28, 1962.

NAME

Mevlevi Tekke / Lodge Museum

LOCATION

Kyrenia Avenue / Kyrenia Gate

DATE INAUGURATED

1962

Background Information

Mevlevi Tekke Museum is the first museum formed by the Turkish Community Council after the Mevlevi Order in Cyprus officially ceased to exist on 15 April 1956, with the handover of Evkaf Administration to the Turkish Cypriot community. Artist and cultural worker Cevdet Cagdas, with the support of a technical team from Konya Turkey, is known to be the first director of the museum, which also housed contemporaneous exhibitions.

NAME

Monument of Martyrs

LOCATION

Near the 'legislative assembly' of the Turkish Cypriot administration

CREATOR

Arif Feridun and Solmaz Feridun

DATE INAUGURATED

28.01.1963

Background Information

The tombstone memorial is situated in the northern part of Nicosia. It is dedicated to the Turkish fighters who lost their lives since 1571, the year Ottomans captured the Island of Cyprus. An inscription on the tombstone reads: "What makes flags is the blood on the land, if there is anything for it, it is the homeland."

NAME

Demetris Lipertis bust

LOCATION

Chrysaliniotissa Public Garden

CREATOR

Andreas Savvides

DATE INAUGURATED

21.04.1963

Background Information

The Demetris Lipertis copper bust was commissioned by EPOK, a group of Greek Cypriot intellectuals formed in 1947 to foster intellectual and artistic relations between Cyprus and Greece. The bust honours the renowned Cypriot poet Demetris Lipertis (1866-1937), who wrote in the Cypriot dialect and is widely recognized for his contributions to the field of poetry.

NAME

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk statue

LOCATION

Parallel to the Venetian walls in the area of Kyrenia Gate

CREATOR

Hüseyin Gezer and Ayer Kaşif

DATE INAUGURATED

29.10.1963

Background Information

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk (1881-1938) considered the founder of the Republic of Turkey, serving as its first President from 1923 until he died in 1938. The statue is located in front of the Kyrenia Gate parallel to the Venetian wall at the northern part of the old city of Nicosia. The statue bears the inscription "Ne Mutlu Türküm Diyene" (How happy is the one who says I am a Turk). The statue was sent as a gift to the Turkish Cypriots from Turkey in 1963.

NAME

Memorial to the Fallen Students of the Pancyprian Gymnasium

LOCATION

Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Nicos Dymiotis

DATE INAUGURATED

03.04.1965

Background Information

The Pancyprian School's Teachers Association of 1959 initiated the construction of a marble monument dedicated to the students at the school who died during the EOKA revolt 1955-1959. The monument was revealed on April 3, 1965, the 10th anniversary of the beginning of the revolt.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Turkish Resistance Organisation
(TMT) Monument 2

LOCATION

St Sophia square

DATE INAUGURATED

1965

Background Information

The monument is circular and made of stone. It displays the emblem of TMT and an inscription that reads "if anyone dies for the land, it's a homeland."

NAME

Museum of Barbarism

LOCATION

Near (former) Shakespeare Avenue

DATE INAUGURATED

01.01.1966 / restored in 1975 /
Complete overhaul and reopening
in 2022

Background Information

The Museum of Barbarism was the house of Dr Nihat Ilhan where his family was murdered in December 1963 during the intercommunal strife.

NAME

Freedom Monument / Liberty
Monument

LOCATION

Podocataro Moat (Venetian Walls)

CREATOR

Ioannis Notaras

DATE INAUGURATED

1967 (placed in 1973)

Background Information

The "Liberty Monument" is a bronze and marble complex consisting of seventeen sculptures created in Florence between 1961 and 1966. The casting was completed in 1966-1967 and the project was installed in 1973, but the unveiling was postponed due to war. The House of Representatives recognized it as the "EOKA Struggle Monument 1955-59" in 1987. The monument depicts a statue of liberty overseeing two EOKA fighters pulling chains to open prison gates and release Greek Cypriot prisoners, peasants, and clergy from British colonial rule.

NAME

Michael Karaolis Memorial

LOCATION

Demosthenis Severis Avenue

CREATOR

Athanasios Minopoulos

DATE INAUGURATED

1967

Background Information

Michael Karaolis (1933-1956) was one of the two first EOKA fighters sentenced to death by hanging, May 10, 1955, along with Andreas Demetriou. The memorial was erected by the Pancyprian Public Servants Trade Union (PASYDY).

NAME

Michael Panayis statue

LOCATION

Central Prison

CREATOR

Marios Garifallakis and
Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

08.07.1967

Background Information

Brass statue of the Prison Guard Michael Panayi who died on December 24, 1963, during the intercommunal strife. The statue was sponsored by the Union of the Central Prison staff.

NAME

Mahatma Gandhi bust

LOCATION

Nehru street, Nicosia Municipal
Gardens

CREATOR

Possibly made in India

DATE INAUGURATED

1972

Background Information

The bust of India's historical leader was donated by the India Government.

NAME

Kostis Palamas statue

LOCATION

Museum Avenue

CREATOR

Vasos Phalireas

DATE INAUGURATED

27.02.1974

Background Information

The seated copper statue of Kostis Palamas was created in 1972 and placed next to the Nicosia Municipal Theatre on February 27, 1974. Kostis Palamas (1859-1943) was a prominent Greek poet whose contribution was significant to the evolution of modern Greek literature. The statue was commissioned by the EPOK (Greek Intellectual Association of the Greeks of Cyprus), an association formed in 1947 by a group of Greek Cypriot intellectuals to tighten the intellectual and artistic relations between Cyprus and Greece.

NAME

Rodion and Miltiades Georgiades
monument (also found as
National or Greek Resistance
Monument - Rodion and Miltiades
Georghiadhes)

LOCATION

Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Nicos Dymiotis

DATE INAUGURATED

24.03.1974

Background Information

The marble monument is dedicated to the two Cypriot brothers Rodionas and Miltiades Georgiades who fought in the Greek front during World War II, were arrested and died in prison. The monument was commissioned by EPOK (Greek Intellectual Association of the Greeks of Cyprus), an association formed in 1947 by a group of Greek Cypriot intellectuals to tighten the intellectual and artistic relations between Cyprus and Greece.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Martyrs' Monument of Küçük Kaymakli

LOCATION

At the centre of the crossroads of Küçük Kaymakli and Yenisehir / Neapolis

CREATOR

Kutcal Cizgen, Burhan Atun

DATE INAUGURATED

25.12.1978

Background Information

A monument dedicated to the Turkish Cypriot fighters who lost their lives through time. The design includes three vertical elements made of exposed concrete. The vertical elements vary in height but are connected to each other by arches. In the middle of these elements, a small pool is set aside for torches.

NAME

Sophia Vempo memorial

LOCATION

Chrysaliniotissa garden

CREATOR

Andreas Savvides

DATE INAUGURATED

30.5.1980

Background Information

Sophia Vempo (1910-1978) was a Greek singer and actress. She remained in people's memory as the "Singer of Victory" because of the national songs she was singing during the Greek-Italian war in 1940. The memorial was an initiative of Cypriot entrepreneur Photos Photiades.

NAME

The Cyprus Classic Motorcycle Museum

LOCATION

44 Granikou street

DATE INAUGURATED

1980

Background Information

The Museum was established by Andreas Nicolaou who started his collection in 1980. Today the collection comprises of more than 350 motorcycles.

NAME

Monument of 'Peace at Home Peace in the World'

LOCATION

Near the Central Bank in the Turkish Cypriot administration

CREATOR

Hasan Emirali, Ekrem Bodamyalizade and Soyer Vikan

DATE INAUGURATED

1981

Background Information

The monument was built in honor of Ataturk's birth 100th anniversary and embodies his principle of "peace at home, peace in the world". It sits upon a pedestal representing five out of the eleven bastions of Nicosia. The configuration of the monument looks like a hand open from the palm towards the sky. It once included a round pool with jetting water to symbolize innocence and purity.

NAME

Georgios Chr. Tsikouris bust

LOCATION

Stasinou Avenue / park

CREATOR

Andreas Savvides

DATE INAUGURATED

1982

Background Information

George Chr. Tsikouris (1945-1970) was a Greek Cypriot resistance fighter who opposed the Greek dictatorship ("Junta"). He and his partner, Maria-Elena Anjeloni, set an explosive device in the American Embassy, which detonated and killed them both on the September 2nd, 1970. The bust was commissioned by the Committee for the Restoration of Democracy in Greece which was formed in Cyprus by Greek Cypriots immediately after junta's coup on 21 April 1967.

NAME

The Byzantine Museum and Art Gallery

LOCATION

Next to the Archbishop's Palace

DATE INAUGURATED

1982

Background Information

The Byzantine Museum is part of the Makarios III Cultural Foundation, attached to the Archbishop's palace. The exhibits of the Museum consist mainly of icons of outstanding Byzantine and post-Byzantine art coming from various churches in Cyprus. The collection, conservation, and promotion of these precious icons, covering the period from the 8th to the 19th century, began in 1967 on the initiative of the Archbishop Makarios III. The Museum is currently under renovation.

NAME

Tito's rock

LOCATION

Eleftheria Square (removed)

CREATOR

Andros Kazamias

DATE INAUGURATED

1982

Background Information

The monument was made for the occasion of the visit of the then President of Yugoslavia in Cyprus, Josip Broz Tito, and was placed in Eleftheria square where Tito and Makarios had addressed the public on 16 October 1964. Tito's rock was removed in 2008 due to the reconstruction of the square and has remained in storage since.

NAME

Turkish Cypriot History, Culture and National Struggle Museum

LOCATION

east of Kyrenia gate

DATE INAUGURATED

1982

Background Information

This museum focuses on the history of the Turkish Cypriot community's struggles spanning from 1878 to the present, displaying documents, photographs, personal artifacts as well as memorabilia relating to the TMT activities.

NAME

"The poet" sculpture

LOCATION

Eleftheria Square

CREATOR

Kostas Varotsos

DATE INAUGURATED

1983

Background Information

This modern sculpture, made of iron and glass was first installed near the Famagusta Gate for the exhibition "Seven Greek artists-A new journey" curated by Efi Strouza. It was later moved to the Carrafa Bastion on the Nicosia Venetian walls in 2018, where it now overlooks the renovated Eleftheria Square. The sculpture was sponsored by the DESTE foundation.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Doros Loizou

LOCATION

Kaniggos street and Stasinou avenue

CREATOR

Nicolaos Kotziamanis

DATE INAUGURATED

30.08.1985

Background Information

The bust commemorates Doros Loizou (1944-1974), an author, poet, journalist, and intellectual, former member of EOKA, who was murdered on August 30, 1974, in the centre of Nicosia. Loizou was an active member of the political party, EDEK, and member of an armed group that was formed to fight the initiators of the coup against President Makarios on 15 July 1974.

NAME

Andis Pernaris bust

LOCATION

Nehrou street

CREATOR

Nicos Dymiotis

DATE INAUGURATED

1986

Background Information

The bust commemorates Antis Pernaris (pen name of Antreas Pavlides, 1903-1980), a writer, journalist and teacher from Nicosia. He worked as a teacher and as a professor. In 1978 he was made honorary president of the National Society of Greek Writers.

NAME

A golden stone for Nicosia

LOCATION

Athinas avenue

CREATOR

Heinrich Brummack

DATE INAUGURATED

11.05.1986

Background Information

As a result of the agreement on cultural exchanges between the Republic of Cyprus and the Federal Republic of Germany, the Municipality of Nicosia and the Municipality of Cologne in collaboration with the Goethe-Institut organized a series of cultural events, part of which was the creation and installation of the work "A golden stone for Nicosia" by the artist himself.

NAME

Constantinos Spyridakis bust

LOCATION

Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Andreas Savvides

DATE INAUGURATED

18.05.1988

Background Information

Constantinos Spyridakis (1903-1976) was one of the most prominent educational figures in Cyprus. He served many years in the post of the Principal of the Pancyprian Gymnasium, while in 1965, he became the first Minister of Education of the newly established Republic of Cyprus. The bust was commissioned by EPOK (Greek Intellectual Association of the Greeks of Cyprus), an association formed in 1947 by a group of Greek Cypriot intellectuals to tighten the intellectual and artistic relations between Cyprus and Greece and of which Spyridakis served as President, and the "Stasinou" Greek teachers' association.

NAME

Dr Fazil Küçük statue

LOCATION

Inönü square,next to Kyrenia Gate

CREATOR

Dr Tankut Öktem and Ali Semi

DATE INAUGURATED

27.01.1989

Background Information

Dr Fazil Küçük (1906-1984) was a Turkish Cypriot politician who served as the first and only until today, Vice President of the Republic of Cyprus. The bronze sculpture is located on a stone platform and features statues of Fazil Küçük and a young girl holding flowers. The girl symbolizes the members of the Turkish Cypriot Community in Cyprus, while the monument embodies confidence. This arrangement is regarded as the first in a public open space in the northern part of Nicosia.

NAME

Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia

LOCATION

Hippocrates street, "Laiki Geitonia" ("Traditional Neighbourhood")

DATE INAUGURATED

20.04.1989

Background Information

The Leventis Municipal Museum presents the history and social development of the city of Nicosia from the Chalcolithic (c. 3000 BC) through the Medieval and Ottoman eras to the present day. It was founded in 1984 by the Municipality of Nicosia and the Anastasios G. Leventis Foundation, on the initiative of the then Mayor of Nicosia, Lellos Demetriades.

NAME

State Gallery for Contemporary Art-Majestic

LOCATION

Kritis street

DATE INAUGURATED

29.06.1990

Background Information

The idea for a gallery of contemporary Cypriot art was formed in 1962, but it was not established at that time due to the political situation. In the early 1980s, representative examples of Cypriot art were collected and eventually exhibited in a temporary gallery. The State Gallery was then inaugurated in 1990 in a neoclassical building with plans to develop it into a State Museum of Contemporary Art. The Art Gallery is expanding into two spaces: the neoclassical building on Kritis & Stasinou Street, 'State Gallery-Majestic' and the SPEL building on Ammochostou street in Nicosia.

NAME

PEO Working Class Heroes Monument

LOCATION

PEO building Achermou Street

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

1991

Background Information

The monument was unveiled on November 3, 1991 by the President of Cyprus, George Vassiliou, during the 21st conference for the 50th anniversary of the Pancyprian Federation of Workers (PEO). Its plaque reads: "To the invisible heroes of the working class".

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Zubeyde Ali Riza (Ataturk's mother) bust

LOCATION

Front garden of the 'Temmuz Lycees' facing the main road

DATE INAUGURATED

1990s

Background Information

Zübeyde Hanım (1856-1923) was Mustafa Kemal Atatürk's mother. The inscription reads: "We welcome the eldest of Turkish mothers in Cyprus".

NAME

Constantinos Leventis column

LOCATION

Byron avenue / Leventis square

DATE INAUGURATED

1990s

Background Information

Constantinos Leventis was a Greek Cypriot entrepreneur and one of the greatest benefactors of the island.

NAME

Vladimiros Kafkarides bust

LOCATION

Nicosia Municipal Gardens

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

1993

Background Information

Actor and director Vladimiros Kafkarides (1932-1983) was one of the founders of the modern Cypriot theatre.

NAME

Themistocles Dervis bust

LOCATION

Town Hall Gardens

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

1993

Background Information

Themistocles Dervis (1894-1968) was a Greek Cypriot doctor and politician. He served as (appointed or elected) Mayor of Nicosia for 27 years and was the founder of the right-wing Cyprus National Party (KEK). The marble bust was an initiative of Nikos Karydis, Nicosia Municipality employee and friend of Dervis.

NAME

Michalakis (Michael) Karaolis bust

LOCATION

The English School

CREATOR

Giorgos Kyriacou

DATE INAUGURATED

1993

Background Information

Michalakis (Michael) Karaolis (1933-1956) was one of the two first EOKA fighters sentenced to death by hanging, on May 10, 1955, along with Andreas Demetriou. The memorial, initiated by the English School at which he studied, was revealed on May 10, 1996 on the 40th anniversary of his death by the then President of the Republic of Cyprus, Glafkos Clerides.

NAME

Nicosia Municipal Arts Centre
(NiMAC)

LOCATION

Palia Elektriiki street

CREATOR

Nicosia Municipality / Pierides
Foundation

DATE INAUGURATED

1994

Background Information

NiMAC [Nicosia Municipal Arts Centre, Associated with the Pierides Foundation / Old Powerhouse] is housed in the renovated building of the Old Powerhouse, located in the historical centre of Nicosia after an agreement between the Electricity Authority of Cyprus and Nicosia Municipality. It is the oldest and largest Contemporary Art Centre of the island. Its architectural restoration and conversion into a beautiful art and cultural space was awarded the Europa Nostra Award in 1994.

NAME

"The Resolution" sculpture

LOCATION

Ledra street

CREATOR

Theodoulos Gregoriou

DATE INAUGURATED

1995

Background Information

"The Resolution" sculpture, made of cement and aluminum, is a protest to the violation of human rights. On the round cement basis of approximately a metre in height, part of the text of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is written in embossed Greek letters. A stack of steel lances diagonally arranged hit the centre of the text, symbolically destroying it. The sculpture was donated by the Culture Services of the Ministry of Education and Culture on the European Cultural Month.

NAME

Monument to the Fallen Cypriot
Volunteers of the Second
World War

LOCATION

Demosthenis Severis Avenue,
PASYDY

DATE INAUGURATED

14.05.1995

Background Information

The Pancyprian Association of WWII Fighters erected this marbled memorial to honour the 35.000 Cypriot volunteers who lost their life in the Second World War and are buried outside Cyprus.

NAME

Ourania Kokkinou bust

LOCATION

Outside the Faneromeni School

CREATOR

Angelika Korovesi

DATE INAUGURATED

12.07.1996

Background Information

The bust of Ourania Kokkinou, a prominent teacher and member of EOKA was inaugurated on July 12, 1996 by the Archbishop of Cyprus, Chrysostomos I, in the presence of the President of the Republic, Glafkos Clerides. The bust was the result of a competition organised by the Initiative Group for the erection of a bust/monument of Ourania Kokkinou - presided by architect Andreas Philippou- which secured a permit from the Nicosia Municipality for the site of the monument. The cost was estimated at 50,000 pounds. To collect the amount, a Financial Committee was established chaired by Tassos Papadopoulos, Member of Parliament. The Commission decided to request voluntary offers and accounts were opened in Cypriot banks.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Iacovos Patatsos statue

LOCATION

Eleneion School

CREATOR

Christos Symeonides-Chrisimos

DATE INAUGURATED

1996

Background Information

Iacovos Patatsos (1934-1956) was an EOKA fighter, sentenced to death by hanging, on August 9th, 1956, for his active role in the armed revolt against the colonial rule. He was a graduate of the Eleneion elementary school. The statue was commissioned by a committee formed for this occasion.

NAME

Dr Fazil Küçük Museum

LOCATION

Kyrenia Avenue

DATE INAUGURATED

14.03.1997

Background Information

The "Dr Fazil Küçük Museum" is a private museum, placed in Kyrenia Avenue and constructed with Küçük's family contributions in Küçük house and office . It showcases personal belongings of Küçük. Dr Fazil Küçük (1906-1984) was a Turkish Cypriot politician who served as the first and only until today, Vice President of the Republic of Cyprus.

NAME

Andronikos Melachrinos Bust

LOCATION

Central Prison

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

1999

Background Information

Andronikos Melachrinos (1952-1974) was a Greek Cypriot soldier who fell in battle during the 1974 war. The statue was erected by the Union of the Central Prison staff.

NAME

Kyriakos Matsis statue

LOCATION

Outside the Presidential Palace

CREATOR

Evangelos Moustakas

DATE INAUGURATED

2002

Background Information

Kyriakos Matsis (1926-1958) was an EOKA fighter who died during a battle in Dikomo village, on November 19th, 1958. One of the main roads leading to this memorial bears his name. The monument with a brass statue was erected by the Council of the Historical Memory of the EOKA struggle (SIMAE).

NAME

Greek Goddess Athena statue

LOCATION

Aegean avenue /
Pallouriotissa school

DATE INAUGURATED

2002

Background Information

Brass statue of Greek Goddess Athena, commissioned by the Committee for the Restoration of Democracy in Greek which was formed in Cyprus by Greek Cypriots immediately after junta's coup on 21 April 1967. The statue was inaugurated by the Mayor of Nicosia Michalakis Zambelas and Mayor of Athens Demetris Avraamopoulos in the context of the twining between the two cities.

NAME

Efrosini Proestou bust "Kyra tis Lapithou" (Lady of Lapithos)

LOCATION

Ledra Palace crossing

CREATOR

Charis Evangelou

DATE INAUGURATED

2002

Background Information

Efrosini Proestou (1903-1993) was a Greek Cypriot woman known as "Lady of Lapithos" as she managed to save and take care of twelve soldiers who were trapped behind enemy lines during the Battle of Lapithos on August 6, 1974, for a month. A bronze bust was initiated by these soldiers and sponsored by the displaced Municipality of Lapithos.

NAME

Demosthenis Mitsis bust

LOCATION

Arch. Makarios III avenue

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

2003

Background Information

Demosthenis Mitsis (1848-1923) was a Greek Cypriot entrepreneur and one of the island's greatest benefactors. In 1912, he founded the Mitsis High School in the village of Lemythou. The bust was erected by the Managing Council of the Mitsis School on the 90th anniversary of the school.

NAME

Shot putter

LOCATION

Byron avenue / Greek Embassy

CREATOR

Aristides Patsoglou

DATE INAUGURATED

2005

Background Information

Modern art sculpture commissioned by the Committee for the Restoration of Democracy in Greece which was formed in Cyprus by Greek Cypriots immediately after junta's coup on 21 April 1967.

NAME

286 MIB monument

LOCATION

Stasinou Avenue

CREATOR

Andreas Ioannou

DATE INAUGURATED

2006

Background Information

Memorial dedicated to the ten fallen and thirty missing soldiers of the 286 Motorised Infantry Battalion during the 1974 war. The memorial was erected by the 286 Motorised Infantry Battalion Fighters Association.

NAME

Column for the fallen of the Orthodox Christian Youth Union (OHEN)

LOCATION

OHEN Faneromeni

DATE INAUGURATED

2007

Background Information

The marble column was commissioned by the Faneromeni Church Committee. The Orthodox Christian Organisations of Youth (OHEN) in Cyprus were formed, initially in Nicosia in 1947, with the encouragement of the Church. They had a missionary, social, humanitarian, and national role. Their girls' branch was much bigger than the boys' one and had, by the end of the 1950s, around 20,000 members. OHEN had a prominent role in the EOKA anti-colonial revolt

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Sculpture

LOCATION

Audit Service building

CREATOR

Theodoulos Gregorio

DATE INAUGURATED

2007

Background Information

Modern art sculpture commissioned by the Cultural Services of the Ministry of Education and Culture.

NAME

TMT Monument

LOCATION

Gönyeli/ Kioneli

CREATOR

Selami Sozen

DATE INAUGURATED

2007

Background Information

The monument was made with exposed concrete and a circular platform featuring symbolic representations of the bastions of old Nicosia and the flags of TMT groups. Its shape resembles that of an obelisk, gradually thinning towards the top.

NAME

José Marti memorial

LOCATION

Stasinou Avenue

CREATOR

possibly made in Cuba

DATE INAUGURATED

2007

Background Information

José Marti (1853-1895) was a national hero of Cuba. The memorial consists of the figure of José Martí embossed in a star. He was a Cuban national hero and founder of the Cuban Revolutionary Party. He fought against the Spanish in Cuba.

NAME

Frixos Petrides bust

LOCATION

Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

2007

Background Information

Frixos (1915-1998) was a prominent teacher who served as Minister of Education of the Republic of Cyprus. In 1960 he was promoted to head of the Pancyprian Gymnasium, a position in which he served for eight years. From 1960 to 1970 he served as chairman of the board of directors of the Cyprus Broadcasting Corporation, and from 1970 until 1972, as Minister of Education. The bust was placed following an initiative of the 1974 Graduates of the Pancyprian Gymnasium.

NAME

Unnamed statue

LOCATION

Asmaalti Square

DATE INAUGURATED

30.11.2007

Background Information

Abstract stone figure on small plinth.

NAME

Archbishop Makarios III statue

LOCATION

Holy Archbishopric of Cyprus

CREATOR

Apostolos Fanakides

DATE INAUGURATED

2008

Background Information

The Archbishopric of Cyprus placed this marbled statue of Archbishop Makarios III in the Archbishopric's front yard after the removal of the ten-metre statue of Makarios that was put there in 1987. Archbishop Makarios III (1913-1977) was the Archbishop of the Church of Cyprus from 1950 until 1977 and first President of the Republic of Cyprus, from 1960 until 1977.

NAME

Nicos Kranidiotis bust

LOCATION

Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Konstantinos Palaiologos

DATE INAUGURATED

2008

Background Information

Nicos Kranidiotis (1911-1997) was a prominent Greek Cypriot writer and diplomat, and one of Archbishop Makarios III main advisors. The marble bust was an initiative of the Council of the Historical Memory of the EOKA struggle (SIMAE) and Nicos Kranidiotis family.

NAME

Andreas Zakos bust

LOCATION

Severis Library, Pancyprian Gymnasium

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

2008

Background Information

Andreas Zakos (1931-1956) was an EOKA fighter, one of the fighters sentenced to death by hanging, on August 9th, 1956. The marble bust was erected in front of the Severis Library inside the Pancyprian Gymnasium, on the initiative of the Council for the Historical Memory of the EOKA struggle (SIMAE).

NAME

Stavros Stylianides bust

LOCATION

Chrysaliniotissa Garden

CREATOR

Leonidas Spanos

DATE INAUGURATED

2009

Background Information

Stavros Stylianides (1927-1957) was an EOKA fighter, from Yialousa, who died on August 18 1957, at the age of 29 during a bomb explosion. The bronze bust was commissioned by the Yialousa Association.

NAME

Flamingo sculpture

LOCATION

Outside the Walled City Museum, near Kyrenia Gate.

DATE INAUGURATED

2000s

Background Information

No information available

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Marios Tokas & Kostas Montis busts

LOCATION

Stasinou Avenue

CREATOR

Giorgos Mavrogenis

DATE INAUGURATED

2009

Background Information

Marios Tokas (1954-2008) was a Greek Cypriot composer, one of the most acknowledged Cypriot composers with an admirable career in Cyprus and Greece. He worked with many prominent artists and put music to the poems of renowned Greek, Greek Cypriot and Turkish Cypriot poets. The bronze bust was erected by the Photos Photiades Scientific and Cultural Foundation. Kostas Montis (1914-2004) was a Greek Cypriot poet, one of the most renowned poets of Cyprus. The bronze bust was erected by the Photos Photiades Scientific and Cultural Foundation.

NAME

National Sovereignty Monument

LOCATION

At the opposite end of an axis to Ayios Dometios crossing

CREATOR

Polyxene Kasda, Dr. Tankut Oktem, Pinar Oktem Dogan

DATE INAUGURATED

21.07.2009

Background Information

The monument's base is circular and represents the island of Cyprus. Its vertical expression is a rounded wall covered by beige marble on the west side and a circular platform in the middle. In plan, these shapes form a crescent and a star. One flag of the Turkish Cypriot administration and 16 Turkish flags adjoin the statue to represent the sixteen Turkish states established in history.

NAME

Gunsel Art Museum and statues

LOCATION

(Former)Shakespeare Avenue

DATE INAUGURATED

2000s

Background Information

No information available

NAME

"Authors of the Avenue" Monument to William Shakespeare and Mehmet Akif Ersoy

LOCATION

Former Shakespeare Avenue

CREATOR

Senih Cavusoglu

DATE INAUGURATED

2000s

Background Information

The monument is dedicated to English playwright, poet and actor William Shakespeare (1564-1616) -the road was formerly known as Shakespeare avenue- and Mehmet Akif Ersoy (1873-1936), Turkish and pan-islamist poet, writer, academic, politician and author of the Turkish national anthem.

NAME

Bülent Ecevit statue

LOCATION

In front of the high school that bears the same name

CREATOR

Eray Okkan

DATE INAUGURATED

26.08.2010

Background Information

Mustafa Bülent Ecevit was a Turkish politician, statesman, poet, writer, scholar, and journalist, who served as the Prime Minister of Turkey four times between 1974 and 2002. He served as prime minister in 1974, 1977, 1978-1979, and 1999-2002 (28.5.1925-5.11.2006). Some of Ecevit's poems are carved on the base of the statue. It was erected with support from the the local administration of the Turkish Cypriot community of Nicosia and Sözlüliler Ocağı, a nationalist society.

NAME

Nicolas Savva Mparri

LOCATION

Agios Andreas

CREATOR

Christos Symeonides-Chrisimos

DATE INAUGURATED

2010s

Background Information

Nicolas Savva Mparri was a Greek Cypriot soldier who died during the 1974 war in the area of Kyrenia.

NAME

Monument to the Fallen and Missing of the 3rd Company of the 211 Infantry Battalion

LOCATION

Ayia Varvara church

CREATOR

Nikos Kouroussis

DATE INAUGURATED

2011

Background Information

Memorial to the Fallen and Missing of the 3rd Company of the 211 Infantry Battalion in the 1974 war. The fallen soldiers were primarily from the areas of Neapolis, Trachonas, Omorfita and Kaymakli. The Memorial was commissioned by the Battalion's Association.

NAME

The Pancyprian Gymnasium museums

LOCATION

Next to the Pancyprian Gymnasium

DATE INAUGURATED

1893, renovated recently

Background Information

The Museums of The Pancyprian Gymnasium are located in the historical center of Nicosia and consist of twelve rooms. The school's first attempt to establish a museum is dated back to 1893, with the donation of a collection of rocks by the consul of Greece in Cyprus. The school acquired additional items over time, through purchase or donation, which were sorted and maintained by teachers. The Pancyprian Gymnasium is the oldest secondary school in Cyprus.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

The Monument of the First Step

LOCATION

In a small round-shaped plaza in Trachonas / Neapolis

CREATOR

Ahmet Ünsal, Celal Deniz

DATE INAUGURATED

27.01.2011

Background Information

The Monument of the First Step is a commemoration of four Turkish Cypriots who were killed in 1957 and recognized as martyrs in the Turkish Cypriot Community. The monument was erected by the local administration of the Turkish Cypriot community of Nicosia and the Sönezlerr Quarry. The monument consists of a concrete column with a trapezoid shape and a height of two meters. The column is covered with light-colored marble, and at the top, bronze masks of the martyrs are placed on each of its sides.

NAME

Archbishop Makarios III bust

LOCATION

Ayios Savvas Church

DATE INAUGURATED

2012

Background Information

Archbishop Makarios III (1913-1977) was the first president of the Republic of Cyprus, in office from 1960 until his death in 1977. He was also the Archbishop of Cyprus. A bronze bust of him was erected by the church committee of Ayios Savvas Church. Archbishop Makarios III (1913-1977) was the Archbishop of the Church of Cyprus from 1950 until 1977 and first President of the Republic of Cyprus, from 1960 until 1977.

NAME

The 'Private Ethnographic Museum of Cyprus'

LOCATION

Near EU Programme Support office in the Turkish Cypriot community

DATE INAUGURATED

July 2012

Background Information

Founded by Ergun Pektaş on the site of his factory Rubberex Co Ltd which he has converted into a museum since he closed the business and retired. It contains his collection of different types of furniture, clothing and fine arts.

NAME

Yuri Gagarin bust

LOCATION

Nicosia Municipal Gardens

CREATOR

Vladimir Usov

DATE INAUGURATED

15.04.2013

Background Information

The bust of the Soviet cosmonaut Yuri Gagarin was inaugurated on April, 15 2013, by the Mayor of Nicosia Constantinos Yiorkadjis. The placement of the bust was made following a decision of the Municipal Council and was part of the general strengthening of the relations of Nicosia Municipality with the Moscow Municipality and the friendship of the peoples of the two countries, Cyprus and Russia. Nicosia and Moscow have been twinned cities since 1997 and have held various events both in Nicosia and in Moscow.

NAME

A.G. Leventis Gallery

LOCATION

Anastasios G. Leventis Street

DATE INAUGURATED

2014

Background Information

The Gallery is home to three collections: the Paris Collection and the Greek Collection, acquired by Anastasios G. Leventis himself, and the more recent Cyprus Collection.

NAME

Centre for Visual Arts and Research

LOCATION

Ermou Street

DATE INAUGURATED

2014

Background Information

CVAR is home to the Costas and Rita Severis collections, which include paintings, antique costumes and memorabilia related to Cyprus and neighbouring countries. CVAR also houses a library and research centre with over 10,000 volumes available to scholars and casual readers alike.

NAME

The Fairy Tale Museum

LOCATION

Granikou Street

DATE INAUGURATED

23.2.2017

Background Information

The Fairytale Museum showcases fairy tales, legends, myths, and traditions from Cyprus and beyond. It provides exhibits, educational programs, events, and performances related to these stories. The museum is associated with the Systemic Cyprus Institute, which is focused on theoretical evolution and systemic application.

NAME

State Gallery for Contemporary Art
"SPEL"

LOCATION

Athinas Avenue

DATE INAUGURATED

31.1.2019

Background Information

SPEL is the second building that showcases contemporary Cypriot art through exhibitions. It was originally built in 1965 as a wheat storage but was renovated and opened as an art exhibition space in 2019 with the Christoforos Savva exhibition "Untimely, on Time".

NAME

Walled City Museum

LOCATION

Kyrenia Gate

CREATOR

Possible artist of mentioned sculptures Tolkunbek Esenaliyev commissioned by the Günsel family.

DATE INAUGURATED

15.11.2020

Background Information

The Walled City Museum opened on the 37th anniversary of the unilateral proclamation by the Turkish Cypriot administration. It is located in the old building of the Ziraat Bank, which was restored with the initiative of the Günsel Family. The museum features nine bronze statues, each three metres tall, at the entrance. The first statue above the door represents a triumphant athlete. The other eight statues surrounding the museum exhibit dancers celebrating this victory.

MONUMENTS DOCUMENTED

NAME

Theatre statues (Kemal Tunç & Osman Balikçioğlu)

LOCATION

Kyrenia Gate (in the Walls moat / promenade)

CREATOR

Sevcan Cerkez (artist)

DATE INAUGURATED

2020

Background Information

This sculpture commemorates Kemal Tunç, a theatre actor who created the radio sketches Alikko and Caher. These sketches were broadcast on Bayrak Radio from 1964 to 1972 before being adapted for the theatre stage. The character of Caher was played by actor Osman Balikçioğlu.

NAME

Stone - Part of an olive mill

LOCATION

Outside the Walled City Museum, near Kyrenia Gate.

DATE INAUGURATED

2010s

Background Information

In 2020, a statue of a bull was put there but due to people's outcry, it was soon removed. The public reacted to the sculpture because the private museum erected the statue on its own whim. It was later found out that the walled city museum did not receive permission from the local authorities, and therefore they removed it. It was later installed near Ayios Dometios crossing.

NAME

Salahi Sevket statue

LOCATION

Across the Mula Bastion

CREATOR

Hikmet Berk

DATE INAUGURATED

n.d.

Background Information

The bust commemorates Turkish Cypriot Salahi Sevket who died on 23rd December 1963, in the beginning of the intercommunal strife. Inscription says: "In the resistance of the Turkish society against Greek attacks, on 23.12.63, the righteous Salahi Sevket rose to the rank of martyrdom in this bastion".

NAME

Dt. Haşmet Muzaffer Gürkan bust

LOCATION

On the street that bears the same name, Arabahmet

CREATOR

Tahsin Albulut, Serhan Gazioglu, Omer Kose

DATE INAUGURATED

n.d.

Background Information

The small monument commemorates researcher and writer Haşmet Muzaffer Gürkan who was known for his love of Nicosia. The column and bust are situated at a crossroad with his name. The epitaph includes a map of the walled city of Nicosia and a notation "He was a keen admirer of Nicosia."

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bakshi, Anita. *Topographies of Memories: A new Poetics of Commemoration*. Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017.

Bakshi, Anita. "A shell of memory: The Cyprus conflict and Nicosia's walled city." *Memory Studies* 5, no. 4 (October 2012): 479-496.

Besim, Devrim Yücel and Ayer Kaşif. "An overview of Existing Monuments in Nicosia." *Journal of Cyprus Studies* 19, no. 43 (Spring 2017): 67-81.

W Ryback, W. Timothy, Ellis, S. Mark S and Glahn, Benjamin, eds. *International Bar Association Task Force Report: Contested Histories in Public Spaces: Principles, Processes, Best Practices*, London: International Bar Association, 2021.

Joseph, S. Joseph. *Cyprus: Ethnic Conflict and International Politics*. London: Macmillan Press, 1997.

Karaiskou, Vicky. "Commemorative Sculpture and Ceremonial Behaviors in the Public Sphere: Cyprus as a Case Study." *Sociology Study* 3, no. 12 (December 2013): 920-932.

Koiloran, Moira. "Nationalisms and Embodied Memory in Northern Cyprus." In *Cyprus and its people: nation, Identity, and Experience in Unimaginable Community 1995-1997*, edited by Vangelis Calotychos. Colorado: Westview Press, 1998.

Papallas, Andreas. "Nationalism, Cultural Identities and Urban Conflicts as Shaped within the Contested Space of Nicosia." In *Identity, Belonging and Human Rights: A Multi-Disciplinary Perspective*, edited by Nasia Hadjigeorgiou. United Kingdom: Inter-Disciplinary Press, 2016.

Pollis, Adamantis. "The social construction of ethnicity and nationalism: The case of Cyprus." *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics* 2, no.1 (1996): 67-90.

Stylianou-Lambert, Theopisti and Alexandra Bounia. *The Political Museum: Power, Conflict, and Identity in Cyprus*. New York: Routledge, 2016.

Tselika, Evanthia. *Conflict Transformation Art: Cultivating coexistence through the use of socially engaged artistic practices*. Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, Report 4, 2019.

Online documents

Theodoulou, M. "Nicosia bids farewell to a towering figure", *The National News*, October 22, 2008. [linkhttps://www.thenationalnews.com/world/europe/nicosia-bids-farewell-to-a-towering-figure-1.561157](https://www.thenationalnews.com/world/europe/nicosia-bids-farewell-to-a-towering-figure-1.561157)

United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Island, Greece and Turkey and Cyprus, No.5475. *Treaty of Guarantee*, 16 August 1960, United Nations -Treaty Series, p.2 <https://peacemaker.un.org/cyprus-greece-turkey-guarantee60#:~:text=This%20treaty%20is%20part%20of,%20partition%20of%20the%20Island>. Accessed 10.07.2023

Notes:

1 Disclaimer: CYENS Centre of Excellence is a research and innovation centre that operates under the motto "Inspired by Humans Designed for Humans". Its vision is to produce world-class research that drives innovation towards a social and economic benefit, while conducting excellent, internationally competitive scientific research in the areas of visual sciences, human factors and design, communication, and artificial intelligence. It is supported by the European Commission, the Republic of Cyprus, and its founding partners: the Municipality of Nicosia, the Max Planck Institute for Informatics (MPI), University College London, the University of Cyprus, the Cyprus University of Technology, and the Open University of Cyprus. DeepNic is a research project, hosted by CYENS and funded by the Research Promotion Foundation. In conjunction with key socio-political events that occurred between 1960 and 2020, it investigates the evolution and transformation of Nicosia's urban centre in three thematic areas: demography, business activity and monument building. DeepNic's research team includes both Greek Cypriots and Turkish Cypriots and primary research was conducted across the Green Line. The project acknowledges the suffering that the people of the island have experienced during the island's recent history and that terminology related to the conflicts between the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities can be politically charged. CYENS aims to be objective and to use scientific inquiry as a tool that transcends political and social differences. Taking all this into consideration, CYENS' decision for any publications derived from the DeepNic project is to use language that is as inclusive and respectful towards as many sensibilities as possible, with multiperspectivity and critical thinking as guiding principles, and to present DeepNic's research results objectively, without any intention to offend or alienate. With this project, CYENS does not, in any way, afford any entities recognition that has not been granted by law.

2 Thanks: The production of this overview would not have been possible without the contribution of Iliana Koulafeti and Loizos Kapsalis for their valuable feedback and cross checking.

3 Acknowledgments: Much information on the monuments in Nicosia was taken from:

Dr. Vicky Karaiskou, Associate Professor Open University of Cyprus, Research project "Cyprus: land of memories, places of art" <http://publicart.ouc.ac.cy/>

